

Some reflections on the Riemst - Caestert / Visé – Caster fortification part 1

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Image 1. The location of Caestert at the border between Flanders and Wallonie, just south of the Dutch city of Maastricht; the location is part of the communities of Visé and Riemst

Summary

This article is based on some recent field -observations in the Riemst –Caestert (or the Walloon part Visél – Caster) area and on remarks from the RAAP report nr 1769.(see reference below the text).

Coincidental events could be responsible for the lack of archaeological finds from the surface of the Caestert plateau near the communities of Kanne and Visé in Belgium. The main reasons for the lack of such finds would be:

1. The historical erosion on the plateau mainly in western and southern direction, following a natural sloping gradient
2. The human activities, like leveling and strengthening of the fortification directly after the destruction of the Iron Age occupation – (which could as well have been deserted before)
3. The collapse of sinkholes, especially in the highest part of the plateau, a process that is still ongoing
4. The (assumed) limited Iron Age activities at the plateau, coinciding with the function of the location other than large scale households, such as a hiding fortress or a sanctuary
5. The immediate decrease of strategic interest of the site after the rebuilding of the place by the Romans in the first decades before Christ, and the occurring rise of cities like Tongres and Maastricht at the same time (connected by a main road, the so called Via Belgica).

6. Erosion of the surface after the Roman period, by land use for the Medieval castle(s) and afterwards

Brief introduction

The Iron Age fortification of Caestert has been investigated by Mr. Heli Roossens, between 1973 and 1975 (Roossens, 1976). Dendrochronological research on the carbonized wood that was thought to be part of a former 'Ehrang' type wall fortification, as it was found together with pieces of burned clay, proved initially that it was burnt wood from 57 BC. However, a new study from 1980 (1) placed the date of the carbonized wood in 31 BC., thereby determining the fortification may be unlikely to rank the location as "Attuatuca".(2)

It can be concluded that there is a good chance the dated parts of the southern part of the reinforcement, were built and used, as expected, in the period Late Iron Age (La Tène II and III) - Gallo Roman times, i.e. somewhere between approximately 250 and 40 BC,(RAAP report 1769, 2008. pp 100). The name *Caestert* in Dutch or *Caster* in French is referring to a Roman military camp. that was not only located at the hill " Pietersberg", but covered a wider area including a part of the Maas river area, just south of the Dutch village of Eijsden, where we still find the fieldname "Laag Caestert"; this latter place could have served as a controlled military area , linked to the Caestert area uphill, e.g. for supplies by the Maas river.

Short-term prehistoric activities at a major structure?

It is clear, many features from the upper stratigraphy at the field are lost, due to both erosion (historical erosion by land-use and by collapses of old marble- mine shafts, causing large sinkholes) and human activities at the plateau, especially within the part of the ramparts.

Between 1973 and 1975 Roossens collected Neolithic artifacts from pits and from ramparts indicating the soil has been moved in later times, after the Neolithic, possibly during the building of the walls.

Current finds of carbonized wood and accompanying burned clay from the ramparts sometimes are accompanied by finds of handmade sherds that are most likely from the Iron Age period and would have belonged to the original inhabitants of the Caestert plateau.(see image below).The finds of these sherds at those location where carbonized wood appears, underlines the outcome of the RAAP research, which conclusions were that supposed habitation will have concentrated, especially in the southern part of the fortification.

Image 2. Carbonized wood from an eroded horizon, found together with burned loam (in the purple outline) from Iron Age structures, found together with handmade sherds from large vessels

Why so little evidence?

There is the question how it is possible such a major structure as the ramparts show so few finds in the archaeological record for the Gallo Roman period. Not only there are only few shards found within the fortification, metal detecting also provides very little in the area (see: Verhoeven, 2008).

This article will discuss a possible explanation for this little evidence by archaeological correlate in the field.

At first, the short- time activities and limited habitation of the location would have caused little archaeological remains in the field. This applies both to the Iron Age period, and for the period of use as a Roman military camp. A modest Iron Age fortification possibly only would have been used for short periods, since the platform was not exactly a fertile area (compare this with the nearby St. Pietersberg) so possibly it was used solely because of its strategic position between Maas and Jeker. This would partly explain the low quantity of Iron Age finds. The Romans would possibly have conquered the Iron age site in 31 BC, in which case during the attack the wooden framework has been burned or the fortification was deliberately set into fire by the Eburons. Afterwards a large part of the plateau must have been leveled by large excavations, to extend and rearrange the site, forming the base of a Roman fortification. In addition, the upper horizons (with possible traces from previous periods) of the plateau would have been excavated and transported for the construction of the large earth wall, that rises up to 7 meters above the surrounding area. In such case, possible finds from the former surface of the plateau nowadays are located in the earth wall, or even in the lower (lowest) basic parts of it. This also explains the large amount of gravels at the surface of the main part of the plateau. Certainly, this would explain why at the plateau no or very little (metal) discoveries are made, not from the Iron Age, nor from the Roman period, notwithstanding the fact we might expect many surface- finds from a location like this.(3)

This also presupposes that *almost immediately* after the construction of the

fortification by the Romans, its function as a military camp would have been lost, especially when the Dutch river area became the front line (Dutch: Liemers, the Roman frontier zone of the north). (4) In fact, it is even also possible the fortification never really has been *used* by the Romans, maybe it could be considered as an *unfinished* fortification, superseded by new provided strategic insights.

In the images below a brief visualization is given as an assumption, based on the lack of finds and visible stratigraphy both at the plateau and the earth wall structure. The nearby village of Kanne however is well known for Roman (surface) finds (like near the cemetery, around the ancient main road "Heirbaan" and in the area of the Roman tumulus at Eben Emael- Kanne) as well as from locations like the cellar of the Chateau Neercanne which is of a Roman origin (Wolters, 1989).

A conclusion from this theory could be:

The imposing earth rampart could indeed have been the result of a short term use both in the Iron Age, as after the destruction and rebuilding by the Romans. This coincidence of events made it happen that we still find an imposing fortification, but with very little accompanying finds.

Schematic view.

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Schematic view of the fortification at the plateau of Visé -Caestert (1, 2)
 1 = original situation, where the plateau was covered by a thick loess layer (represented in light grey), overlaying a gravel layer (dark grey) that was located on a cretaceous bedrock (squares pattern)
 2 = adaptations on the plateau during the Iron Age i.e. fortification walls and an entrance, to be used as an escape site during wars, or maybe to serve as a sacred place; an inner wall structure has been noticed at the highest level of the plateau

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Schematic view of the fortification at the plateau of Visé - Caestert (3,4)
 3= The demolition of the Iron Age structures by the Romans in 31 BC, leaving an archaeological correlate like carbonized wood and burned loam
 4= The leveling of the plateau, using the top surface to re- shape and strengthen the earth wall constructions, wiping out possible traces at the entire leveled plateau surface, leaving very little possibilities to find back objects from the previous Iron Age period, as they are either demolished (fragile handmade sherds) or are located at the inner side or foundations of the wall (while leveling the surface and constructing the rampart, the upper horizons appear in the lowest parts of the newly constructed ramparts). Shortly after the fortification was finished; the strategic interest was gone as the frontier zone had moved to the north (Rhine - Maas area)

Some images.

Image 3. Two examples of handmade Iron Age sherds, found by the author at the Caestert fortification, indicating Iron Age occupation in the period right before the destruction of the site by the Romans. The shards are relatively thick and are parts of large vessels.

Image 4. Metal slag found in the direct vicinity with the handmade sherds, suggesting possible metallurgic activities at the plateau

Image 5. Burned loam with impression of a leaf. This burned loam possibly belonged to the rampart

Image 6. Pottery sherds from Caestert, only top row left is a handmade sherd with dark core; the others are red colored sherds and could belong to the Roman period or later

Notes

- (1) Dendrochronological redating 1980 wood from slot 2 of 1975 (source: Hollstein, 1980: 60).
- (2) Atuatuca, like the lost location that was mentioned in the *Commentarii Rerum in Gallia Gestarum* [*Bello Gallico*]
- (3) Compare this with surface finds at other sites like at Bourguignon (France)
- (4) The march of the Romans continued in the last decade BC, and already in the first decade AD, the frontline was set in the Dutch river area of the Rhine. So the time between the destruction of the Iron Age fortification and the building of the Roman military camp was limited to at most ca 30-40 years, where i.c. we do not know when the Romans have started building the military camp at Caestert.

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Part 2 of these reflections will appear spring 2015